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A GREAT LIFE SPENT ON THE SERVICE OF A NATION

Abstract. B.R. Ambedkar was a leading social reformer and an activist who dedicated his entire life to the betterment of the Dalits and other socially backward classes of India. Ambedkar continuously fought for the eradication of caste discrimination that had spread like a disease in Indian society. As he was born in a socially backward family, Ambedkar was a Dalit who was a victim of caste discrimination and inequality. However, against all odds, Ambedkar became the first Dalit to complete higher education. He then went on and completed college and got a doctorate in economics from London University. He entered politics entirely, aiming to fight for the rights of the backward classes and against the inequality practiced in society. After India became independent, he went on to become the first law minister of free India and the chief architect of the 'Constitution of India'.

Key words: Ambedkar, Dalits, India, service of a nation.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar:

“A great man is different from an eminent one in that he is ready to be the servant of the society.”

Dr. Bhim Rao Ambedkar was one of the great sons of the great Indian nation. He was one of the most learned Indian politicians, at least of his time. He was the first Indian to get a Doctorate in Economics from the London School of Economics as well as a Doctorate from Columbia University (Sud, 2020). In addition, he also got the degree of Barrister-at-Law from Grey's Inn, London. Starting from his childhood, he had a hunger for learning. This intensive motivation made him bring back thousands of second hand books when he went abroad. His personal library at Bombay, Rajgirh, had more than 50,000 books (Sud, 2020).

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar was born on 14 April 1891. He had a very harsh childhood. As he belonged to a low caste, Untouchable family, he could not even

open a tap and drink some water from there. He described this experience of discrimination from an early age, in his later writing, *Waiting for a Visa*, c.1936:

While in the school I knew that children of the touchable classes, when they felt thirsty, could go out to the water tap, open it, and quench their thirst... But my position was separate. I could not touch the tap; and unless it was opened for it by a touchable person, it was not possible for me to quench my thirst (cited in Campion, 2016).

In those days, most of the teachers were often reluctant to engage with Dalit children, often refusing to mark their exams. As the family belonged to the untouchable caste of Mahars, he also had many problems at school. One the way, when they wanted to share food, brought from home, no one was ready to give them water. Bhim knew that he was untouchable and had to follow a certain code of conduct but never before, he had to face such inhuman treatment and humiliations. It made him think about Untouchability. Ambedkar writes in his biography, *Waiting for a Visa*: “This incident has a very important place in my life. I was a boy of nine when it happened. But it has left an indelible impression on my mind” (cited in Sud, 2020). All these difficulties and harshness made him to give a decision. He decided that he would become independent by studying hard and getting a good job. From that day, he gave up his truant habits and dedicated himself to studies. This self-motivation proved to be a life-changing event not only for the boy but also for the nation. His desire for learning made him become the first in his community to graduate High School and went on to study for a BA in Economics and Politics at Bombay University, where he met Sayaji Rao III, the Maharajah of the princely state of Baroda (Campion, 2016). With the sponsorship of this Maharajah Ambedkar continued his further education abroad. First at Columbia University in New York where he completed a Masters and a PhD, and later at LSE was an active advocate of social reforms, including the removal of untouchability. During this period Ambedkar studied economics, history and political science, and wrote on a wide range of topics, including the history of caste in India. There is also evidence in his letters at this time of his belief in education as a path to progress, with a particular emphasis on female education (Keer, 1990).

Dr. Ambedkar raised himself from the lowest rung of the society to an enviable position in Indian political life by his incredible industry and noble self-denial. He searched for knowledge, his heroic struggle for the liberation of a suppressed people in bondage, his verdict on Hinduism, his contribution to Indian thought, history, literature and the Constitution and of his place in the evolution of Hinduism and its phases show that how he dedicated himself to his nation. There are several facts, which we need to highlight here while discussing his personality:

- 1) He played a key role in establishment of Reserve Bank of India in 1935;
- 2) He changed the working hours in India from 14 hours to 8 hours;
- 3) His autobiography is used as a textbook in the Columbia University;

4) He refused to draft Article 370 of the constitution (which gives special status to the state of Jammu & Kashmir) on the grounds that it was discriminatory and against the principles of unity and integrity of the nation

5) He fought for three years to get the comprehensive Hindu Code Bill passed which gave several important rights to women;

6) He was the first to suggest the division of Bihar and Madhya Pradesh;

7) His efforts were pioneering in the development of India's national policy for water and electricity (Pal, 2017).

8) Despite Ambedkar's differences with Congress, when India became independent in August 1947, Prime Minister Nehru invited him to be the first Minister of Law and Justice (Campion, 2016).

The lasting influence of Dr. Ambedkar on Indian social and political events even after his death is evidence of the great significance of his work to contemporary India. As conclusion, we may find the unforgettable legend of a great man in his life story. He mentioned that, "*A great man is different from an eminent one in that he is ready to be the servant of the society*". He dedicated his whole life to his society, became his servant. And the nation of India declared that he is one of the greatest sons of Hindustan.

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PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlarini shakllantirishdan asosiy maqsad klasterlar faoliyatini rivojlantirishga doir masalalar ko'rib chiqilgan. Xususan, mamlakatimizda bu sohada amalga oshirilgan ishlar va natijalar keltirilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: klaster, paxta-to'machilik klasterlari, tikuv-trikotaj sanoati, raqobatbardoshlik, eksport salohiyati.

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WAYS TO INCREASE THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF COTTON- TEXTILE CLUSTERS

Abstract. This article discusses the formation of cotton clusters and discusses development issues. In particular, the work and results carried out in this area in our country are presented.

Key words: cluster, cotton clusters, clothing and knitting industry, competitiveness, export potential.

Agrarindustrial ishlab chiqarishga asoslangan respublikamizning qishloq xo'jaligida chuqur qayta ishlashni va sanoatni rivojlantirmasdan iqtisodiyotimiz ko'rsatkichlarini yuqori ko'tarib bo'lmaydi. Bu jihat Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyev tashabbuslari bilan qabul qilingan 2017-2021 yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustuvor yo'nalish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasida mamlakat iqtisodiyotining raqobatbardoshligini oshirish maqsadida belgilangan ustuvor yo'nalishlarida alohida ahamiyat kasb etgan.

Iqtisodiyotda yangicha, zamonaviy yondashuvlarni joriy etmasdan turib raqobatbardosh mahsulot yaratish mumkin emasligini ta'kidlashimiz zarur.

Taraqqiyot-innovatsiyani talab etadi. "Paxta-to'qimachilik klasteri"- ulkan iqtisodiy loyiha bo'lib, uni shakllantirishdan maqsad- shahar, tuman va viloyat ichida joylashgan bir xil soha korxonalarini va ular bilan yagona texnologik zanjirda bo'lgan ta'lim, ilmiy, injiniring, konsalting, standartlashtirish, sertifikatlashtirish va boshqa xizmatlarni uyg'unlashtirish- innovatsion ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etish asosida raqobatbardosh tovarlar yaratishga yo'nalishtirishdan iboratdir.

Klaster=qo‘shilgan qiymat zanjirining barcha ishtirokchilarini (fermerlar, qayta ishlash korxonalari, eksport qiluvchilar) bir maqsad yo‘lida birlashtirgan korxonalar guruhidir.

Uning maqsadi:

- Mahsulot yetishtirishda zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo‘llash orqali agrotexnik tadbirlarni yangilash, hosildorlikni bir necha barobar oshirish.
- Mahsulot ishlab chiqaruvchilar tomonidan qo‘shilgan qiymat zanjirlarini yaratish.
- va tayyor mahsulotlar eksporti
- Kamroq bilan ko‘proq ishlang. Ishlab chiqaruvchilarning moliyaviy ahvolini yaxshilash.
- ishlab chiqaruvchilarning moddiy-texnik bazasini zamonaviy qishloq xo‘jaligi texnikasi va uskunalari bilan boyitish.

Respublika to‘qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida yuqori va barqaror o‘sish sur‘atlarini ta‘minlash, to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish va o‘zlashtirish, raqobatbardosh mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish va eksport qilish, modernizatsiya qilishning strategik muhim ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan loyihalarini amalga oshirish hisobiga yuqori texnologiyali yangi ish o‘rinlarini yaratish, korxonalarini texnik va texnologik yangilash, ilg‘or «klaster modeli»ni joriy etishga qaratilgan tarkibiy qayta tashkil etishni yanada chuqurlashtirish bo‘yicha tizimli ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

2022-yil 1-aprel holatiga ko‘ra, respublikada 20 ta maxsus iqtisodiy zona (keyingi o‘rinlarda-MIZ), 116 ta kichik sanoat zonalarini direksiyasi (keyingi o‘rinlarda-KSZ), 12 ta texnopark va 440 ta klaster mavjud bo‘lib, ular tarkibiga: MIZ-512 ta korxonalar, 1865 ta MIZ kiradi., texnoparklar-58 va klasterlar-446 ta korxonalar. Respublikada faoliyat yuritayotgan paxta-to‘qimachilik klasterlar viloyatlar kesimida 1-jadvalda ko‘rsatilgan.

1-jadval

2022-2023 yilda faoliyat yuritayotgan paxta-to‘qimachilik klasterlar viloyat bo‘yicha soni

№	Hudud nomi	Paxta-to‘qimachilik klasterlari	Paxta maydoni,ga
1	Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi	11	86791
2	Andijon viloyati	15	78991
3	Buxoro viloyati	11	99220
4	Jizzax viloyati	6	77900
5	Qashqadaryo viloyati	18	136036
6	Navoiy viloyati	4	31655
7	Namangan viloyati	7	63406
8	Samarqand viloyati	11	75356
9	Surxondaryo viloyati	11	72370
10	Sirdaryo viloyati	9	75500
11	Farg‘ona viloyati	13	82080
12	Toshkent viloyati	6	72161